

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

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The 21st International Conference on Harmful Algae

Closing ICHA 2025

Time flies, and the 21st International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA 2025) ended several days ago. This year's event took place in Punta Arenas from October 19th to 24th, 2025, at the Hotel DREAMS del ESTRECHO, located on the shores of the Strait of Magellan.

The conference brought together 345 researchers, decision-makers, and professionals from industry and technology-development sectors related to the study of harmful algae, representing 46 countries. While a much large number of HAB scientists had registered to attend, senior government workers from notably the US and Europe ultimately were not given travel approval, and others encountered visa problems. Still, it was encouraging to see so many new young faces attracted to our exciting HAB discipline, altogether creating a very friendly conference atmosphere.

Between Sunday, October 19th, and Friday, October 24th, 135 oral presentations, 180 posters, and 41 ignite talks were given, distributed across 15 thematic areas. In addition, eight workshops were held, one of them prior to the conference, from October 13th to 17th. Each day was enlivened by one or two keynote lectures, and on Monday

the 20th and Wednesday the 22nd, both in the afternoon, the conference, for the first time, extended its reach to the local community with outreach activities. These activities were aimed at both the general public and high school students in the upper grades of Punta Arenas, providing attendees with an engaging and motivating opportunity to learn about harmful algae, both nationally and globally, and their impacts on public health and aquaculture.

Our gratitude goes to the International Advisory Board and the nearly one hundred colleagues who chaired the 42 sessions that comprised the various components of the conference. And of course, we extend our thanks to our national colleagues who contributed to giving this ICHA the distinctive characteristics and unique perspectives of those of us who shine from the South.

Without a doubt, ICHA 2025 was an opportunity to exchange experiences, motivate young researchers, and reconnect with old friends and acquaintances. It was also a unique occasion to admire the beauty of the Magallanes landscape and wildlife, at the southern tip of the American continent. And the story will continue in other parts of the world, with the next ICHA in Aber-

Participants in the ICHA 2025 Conference are welcome with a Chamamé, the deep-rooted Gaucho folklore born in Patagonia, now part of UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage (photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

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Group photo of participants in the 21st International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA), Punta Arenas, Chile, 19–24 October 2025.

Dedmer Van de Waal, ISSHA President, thanks the Local Organizers of the Conference: Pamela Carbonell, Catharina Alves-de-Souza, Máximo Frangopulos and Leonardo Guzmán (ICHA 2025 Chair) (photo C Band-Schmidt).

deen, Scotland. We are grateful for the opportunity to have had the responsibility of organizing such an important scientific conference on harmful algae. It is a memory that will remain with us for years to come and will be part of the history of science in Patagonia.

Leonardo Guzmán, Chair of the 21st ICHA Local Organizing Committee, Instituto de Fomento Pesquero (IFOP), Centro de Estudios de Algas Nocivas (CREAN), Padre Harter 574, Puerto Montt, Chile

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Enjoying the ICHA 2025 Conference dinner
(photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

"Old HAB soldiers never die". Senior HAB Statesmen Don Anderson, Gustaaf Hallegraef, and Allan Cembella share a glass of wine at the Ice Breaker party (photo DM Anderson).

Old virtual friends finally meet. Vera Trainer (Past ISSHA President) and Christine Band-Schmidt (Chair Organizing Committee 19th ICHA, Mexico) (photo C Band-Schmidt).

Alejandro Clément, Yolanda Pazos and experts from the EU Reference Laboratory on Marine Biotoxins in Vigo (front row) with Bernd Krock and Philipp Hess in the back (photo Y Pazos).

ICHA 2025 Beyond Science

An important part of ICHA 2025 was the proximity of many interesting sites for participants to visit in the Magallanes region of southern Chile. Notable among these were the spectacular Torres del Paine National Park, a site visited by many in long one-day excursions from Punta Arenas, as well as longer trips based out of the picturesque city of Puerto Natales. Some conference participants visited the park by car or bus, while multiple more adventurous groups hiked and camped, getting a close-up view of the amazing scenery, considered by some to be the 8th wonder of the world.

Fig. 1. A popular ICHA 2025 conference excursion was a visit to Magdalena Island, home to thousands of Magellanic penguins sharing their habitat with gulls, skuas and cormorants (photo G Hallegraeff) and Santa Marta with its colony of sea lions (photo J Diogene).

Fig. 2. A. Sunrise in Torres del Paine (Dave Ralston and Mike Brosnahan). B. American participants group in a boat trip to the Grey Glacier (photos DM Anderson).

Another attraction of ICHA 2025 was the city of Punta Arenas with its statues, plazas, and numerous restaurants, serving seafood and Chilean beef, accompanied by excellent Chilean wines.

Fig. 3. Chilean food and wine were a bit hit during ICHA 25! (photos DM Anderson).

ICHA 2025. Scientific Highlights

Fig. 1. Shauna Murray (Sydney, Australia) accepted to lead the big task of collecting information from Chairs and other participants and summarizing it in the Conference Highlights presented here.

The 21st International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA 2025) in Punta Arenas, Chile, provided an ideal showcase for novel insights in HAB research, some of which were driven by the increasingly novel application of key technologies (Fig. 1). On the local and regional scale, HABs are increasingly better understood through integrated technology as varied as remote- and in situ sensing observations (e.g., combining Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB)/Planktoscope and satellite systems), and molecular approaches, including qPCR, metabarcoding and 'omics-based data on gene expression related to metabolic and toxicogenic processes. Methods described at the conference included advanced mass spectrometry (e.g., LC-MS/MS), various biosensors (e.g., fish-gill assay, neuroreceptor binding assays (RBA), and the inclusion of classic environmental water quality, nutrient, and physico-chemical information for modelling. Long-term modelled data are derived and analysed locally but archived in regional and global databases because they may differ substantially between regions.

A further trend is the involvement of more people in HAB science, particularly citizen scientists, shellfish farmers and indigenous communities who assist with data collection, highlighted in

the inspiring plenary talk from **Manu Prakash** and multiple other presentations. Some projects used low-cost data-collection tools; others used this approach combined with high-technology tools such as biosensors, eDNA analyses, and passive samplers. HABs can have significant harmful impacts on coastal communities, justifying their classification as “natural disasters”. Overall, there was a clear emphasis on integrated, interdisciplinary approaches that merge ecological and oceanographic science with technological and socio-economic perspectives for effective HAB management and eventual control.

This conference, attended by 345 participants from 46 countries, also showcased increased development of HAB control and mitigation technologies, and once again highlighted the strong influence of climate change on every aspect of our oceans. It also showed that major HABs in new areas can still surprise us, and that there is much to learn about HAB species and their toxins, even for well-studied species and systems.

Ecology

In the ecology sessions, many studies emphasized the use of integrated laboratory experimentation and field sampling, sometimes in a novel way, to understand the physiological and life cycle drivers of field assemblages.

This included insights into the timing and relative importance of sexual and asexual reproduction of HAB species in the field (**Serena Sung-Clarke**), including drivers of cyst germination and its impacts on population growth and diversity (**Michael Brosnahan**). Analysis of how long-term monitoring data contribute to characterizing ecological niches revealed that microscopy and metabarcoding require an integrated approach (**Keelan Lawlor**). The macro- and micro-nutrient requirements of HAB taxa and new nutrient sources were investigated (**Patricia Glibert**). In the new methods session, the study of mucilage production contributed to a better understanding of the physiological and ecological functions of benthic dinoflagellates and highlighted the relevance of basal metabolites and TEPs in their biofilm dynamics (**Nadia Valeria Herrera**).

Oceanographic drivers were examined in terms of niches of HAB species (**Catharina Alves de Sousa**). Examples included El Niño and La Niña weather systems, upwelling, upwelling relaxation, stratification, freshwater influx, advection, and seasonality. Localities investigated included California (**Ruiz de la Torre**), the Baltic (**Bengt Karlson**), south-eastern Australia (**Dora Vig**), the Pacific Arctic (**Donald Anderson**), the Iberian Peninsula (**Eva Fonfria**) and southern Chile, including a notable plenary summary on Chilean HABs by **Benjamin Suárez** (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Different kinds of vessels, a small one for mussel aquaculture operations (left) and larger boats for artisanal fisheries, in Estero (Sound) de Castro. Castro city (42°28'S, 73°48'W), founded in 1527, is famous for its wooden stilt houses (palafitos). This town is the capital of Chiloé (Los Lagos Region, Chile), the island site of the world's second largest production of mussels (photo Benjamin Suárez).

Fig. 3. The Ecology, Biology, and Biogeography session, chaired by Ian Jenkinson (left to right, 1st left) and Máximo Frangópulos (last, right) with presentations from Jorge Mardones, Patricia Glibert, Catharina Alves-de-Souza and Chris Gobler (2nd to 5th)

The role of HABs in producing favourable or unfavourable water conditions was also examined, such as causing nocturnal oxygen collapse in some mixotrophic systems (**Christopher Gobler**). New sources of nutrients for HABs were discussed, such as off the West Florida Shelf, where so-called “blue holes” are active N-processing hotspots exporting reduced N (notably NH_4^+), facilitating *Karenia brevis* blooms (**Patricia Glibert**). Dense blooms of *Alexandrium ostenfeldii* utilize DON as an N source, while its allelopathic activity toward co-occurring phytoplankton species facilitates N uptake (**Elin Lindehoff**). A critical view on methodologies for nutrient analysis was also discussed (**Wayne Litaker**). Several talks examined the role of microplastic particles from buoys and ropes in suppressing the growth of HAB species or contributing to HAB toxicity (**Jorge Mardones**). Improved strategies for real-time tracking of blooms were presented, focused on *Karenia brevis* and other bloom forming species in Florida (**Katherine Hubbard**). A plenary talk reviewing the role of GEOHAB in stimulating HAB research internationally over many years was given by **Elisa Berdalet**, who brought with her a suitcase of decades of hardcopy IOC-UNESCO reports. The value (and challenges) of the global long time series database HAEDAT was also presented (**Dave Clarke**; Fig. 3).

Cyanobacteria and Freshwater HABs

The cyanobacterial research sessions highlighted the roles of genetic and digital technologies in cyanoHAB detection and research, including molecular tools (**Mark Van Asten**) and digital holography (**Madison Bennett, Aditya Nayak**), and demonstrated that this area of research has come of age over the past 25 years (plenary by **Sandra Azevedo**). A high-resolution 3D imaging approach revealed how nutrients and temperature impact morphology in *Microcystis* spp. (**Ronojoy Hem**). A vast variation of cyanobacterial traits related to nutrient acquisition, photophysiology, and thermal performance across

species and genotypes was shown (**Arnaud Louchart, Carol Waldman**); even within genotypes, cyanobacteria can be highly variable, just like eukaryotic taxa (**Dedmer Van de Waal**), and high ecotype diversity of *Microcystis* adapted to local environmental conditions (**Gabriela Martínez**). The role of micronutrients such as iron in limiting and regulating cyanobacteria and their toxins was also examined (**Charlie Trick, Irena Creed**). A sustainable and innovative management system for toxic cyanobacteria blooms combining preventive strategies and the use of waste cyanobacteria as fertilizers was presented (**Maria G. Antoniou**). Cyanotoxins gained increased attention as a seafood safety concern this year, with new findings such as the first confirmed detection of saxitoxin production in Synechococcales (**Flavio Luis de Oliveira**), and the novel application of LC-HRMS for non-targeted analysis of cyanobacterial biotoxins (**Pearse McCarron**).

Taxonomy and Phylogeny

At the session on Taxonomy and Phylogeny, historical name changes were revisited, with a notable contribution by **Urban Tillmann** concerning the ichthyotoxic haptophyte *Prymnesium parvum*. Phylogenetic relationships within the marine euglenoids belonging to *Eutreptiella* suggested separation into several species (**Sinuhé Hernández Márquez**). Intracellular ultrastructure of the toxigenic and non-toxigenic

Fig. 4. Chairs and oral speakers of the Taxonomy and Phylogeny session. From left to right, Mitsunori Iwataki, Koyo Kuwata, Urban Tillmann, Catarina Churro, Yolanda Pazos (Chair), Liza Campbell (Chair) and Sinuhé Hernández Márquez.

Fig. 5. *Ciguatera* and *Benthic HABS* session chaired by Sam Murray and Catharina Alves-de-Souza (in the middle) with contributions from Amna Ashfaq, Jorge Diogéne, Taiana Darius (first three on the left), Silvia Nascimento and Chiara Melchiorre (last two on the right).

strains of *Azadinium* and *Amphidoma* were compared to identify structures associated with toxin production and the potential for morphological differentiation (Koyo Kuwata). Eleven species of the Amphidomataceae, including four newly recorded in the Northwest Pacific and three newly described species, were reported from Japan (Mitsunori Iwataki). The IOC-FAO IPHAB Task Team on Taxonomy also presented recent updates of the IOC/UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Algae (Catarina Churro; Fig. 4)

Toxicity and Toxicology Research Chemistry and toxins were once again a key theme, from advanced LC-HRMS workflows (Elizabeth Mudge), and LC-MS method innovation designed to monitor multiple classes of toxins (Chiara Melchiorre), through to continued advances in biosensors (Jaume Revérté) for rapid detection of concomitant toxins or the mechanisms of action of cyclic imines (Jordi Molgó). Isolation of polyketide toxins from free-living and symbiotic Symbiodiniaceae was reported (Emily Jolly). Results from Chile's national monitoring programme revealed high levels of YTX and PTX in mussels from Chilean fjords (Fernanda Barrera), along with striking spirulide diversity in *Alexandrium ostentfeldii* from the Beagle Channel (Luis Norambuena). Collectively, these findings remind us that even after decades of research the toxin field continues to evolve.

Toxicological impacts on filter-feeding mollusks, farmed fish, and zooplankton were a focus of several presentations. Species of *Alexandrium* can cause a reduction in filtration rates in juvenile *Magallana gigas*, affecting their feeding rate and survival (Ismavy Castillo). Other harmful taxa, such as *Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa*, *Thalassiosira pseudonana*, and *Heterosigma akashiwo*, have effects on farmed salmonid species, confirming that ROS-mediated oxidative stress is the main cause of pathologies (Diego Caro). Azithromycin (AZT) concentrations can enhance the impacts of toxic cyanobacteria on zooplankton, reflected in fundamental aspects of populations (Michael Celano).

Ciguatera poisoning (CP) remained a key focus, reflecting its continued global relevance and growing impact to non-endemic regions. This included recent progress in ciguatoxin chemistry (Sam Murray), the discovery of novel compounds, improved extraction and quantification techniques (Melanie Roue, presented by Taiana Darius), and the identification of new *Gambierdiscus* species (Christopher Bolch). In her Yasumoto award opening keynote, Mireille Chinain emphasised the value of combining traditional and “Western”-type knowledge in understanding and managing CP; knowledge that includes natural plant-based remedies, awareness of high-risk fishing areas, and recognition of toxic fish by indigenous communities. Outreach activities linking science with local practices were

showcased as an effective way to reduce CP cases. In Brazil, a collaborative effort combining toxin analysis, species identification, and community education has already led to measurable declines in reported poisonings (Silvia Nascimento) (Fig. 5)

A remote plenary presentation from Aifeng Li highlighted the key importance of genomic, transcriptomic, toxin and laboratory culture experiments in elucidating the genetic basis of BMAA (β -N -methylamino-L-alanine) synthesis in diatoms.

Ichthyotoxic HABS

Presentations on ichthyotoxic HABS dealt with functional interactions of ichthyotoxic species in plankton communities and the (“toxic”) mechanisms of collateral damage to fish and other marine fauna. By combining metabolomic and metagenomic approaches linked by gene expression to functional bioassays, it has been possible to develop and apply functional models of toxicogenicity of groups of putative ichthyotoxins, and to use them as templates to explore potency and mechanisms of new ichthyotoxins. For example, among the known polyether ichthyotoxins, the sterolysins—originally only dinoflagellate karlotoxins (KmTx) but also including amphidinols (AM) and more recently haptophyte leadbeaterins (LBT) among others—provide a rich palette for integrative studies on biosynthesis and regulation by polyketide synthases (PKS), and for exploring their membrane-disruptive effects on fish gills and plankton predators and competitors (Anita Solhaug). In a compelling keynote from Bernd Krock, the re-emergence of *Chrysochromulina leadbeateri* in spring 2025 as a major fish-killing bloom taxon was definitively linked to leadbeaterin-1 (LBT-1), and more broadly to sterolysin diversity during fish-killing *C. leadbeateri* blooms in northern Norway (Ingunn Samdal). Rapid advances have also been made in elucidating biosynthetic pathways for PKS-based sterolysins and their eco-evolutionary origins among haptophytes and dinoflagellates (Chris Miles). These pioneering studies presented at ICHA25 are expected to deepen our understanding of global fish-mortality events associated with HABS, such as those involving *Fibrocapsa ja-*

Fig. 6. Participants in a session on Ichthyotoxic HAB mechanisms and biological interactions. Front row (left to right): Lixia Shang, Jiyeon Sung, and Shauna Murray; back, Raph Kudela, and session chairs Thomas Larsen and Kristoff Möller (photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

ponica (Raphidophyceae) from Argentina (**Delfina Aguiar Juárez**) and a HAB in a Northern Tunisian Lagoon (**Afef Fathalli**). An ocean-rheology working group described how polymeric secretions of some HAB species could play a role in killing fish and other organisms through rheotoxicity (**Ian Jenkinson**) (Fig. 6)

Novel insights into the fish-killing mechanisms of harmful algal blooms (HABs) at the HAB organism level were provided from multifaceted and comparative perspectives (**Lixia Shang**). A fundamental mechanism regulating growth and toxigenicity of *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* is physical dynamics driven by turbulence (**Jiyeon Sung**). Successful integration of remote-sensing imaging with classical eco-physiological laboratory studies helped define the ecological footprint, impacts, and dispersion of *Heterosigma akashiwo* blooms in San Francisco Bay, CA, USA (**Raphael Kudela**).

A novel report of an unprecedented large-scale bloom of a *Karenia cristata* in South Australia (now in its eighth month and ongoing) was associated with extensive deaths of marine life and human respiratory irritation (**Shauna Murray**). Isolates of this species were confirmed to produce brevetoxins (BTX) in culture at levels similar or higher than *Karenia brevis*. Because this taxon originally described from the South African coast has never been associated with harmful algal events in

Australia, its origin and potential recurrence remain unknown.

HAB Mitigation and Control

The number of presentations on mitigation and control measures at this ICHA conference continued to increase relative to previous ICHAs. These were comprehensively reviewed in this session (**Vera Trainer**). Modified clays have been shown to efficiently remove *K. brevis* in some studies, and have also been applied to several HAB species in China (**Zhiming Yu, Xiuxian Song**) and in Chilean, Scottish and Norwegian waters (**Ana Flores Leñero**). Some modified-clay approaches have also been shown to degrade toxins, including a study that found over 90% degradation of PSTs from *Alexandrium pacificum* and *Karenia brevis* into lower-toxicity products (**Lianbao Chi**).

HAB Forecasting and modelling

New forecasting approaches using oceanographic data collection, including data refined using machine-learning and fuzzy logic, were shown to improve predictive ability across multiple systems. The use of passive samplers, such as SPATT bags (**Máximo Jorge Frangópulos Rivera, Christopher Miles, Ingunn Samdal**) to collect toxins, as well as other forms of passive samplers for Edna, was introduced, including the involvement of local communities and citizen scientists. Research in New Zealand and North

America showed such community involvement could enhance data collection on HABs and their impacts. New HAB-monitoring systems have been implemented in Mexico, Chile, Colombia, the Baltic Sea, and other regions, and some of these have allowed predictions up to 30 days before toxins appear (**Leonardo Guzmán**; Fig. 7)

HABs and climate change

This conference documented the overwhelming influence of climate change on HABs worldwide. This includes changes in the timing of HAB initiation and termination, in nutrient sources and inputs, and in HAB species distributions. These changes are often complex and region-specific – intensifying blooms in some regions, such as the North Sea (**Andrea Budisa**), becoming persistent such as *Gambierdiscus* populations in the Mediterranean Sea (**Jorge Diogène**), or leading to reduced phytoplankton abundance in other regions, such as areas around New Zealand. These changes are triggered by many different aspects of climate change, including extreme weather events –such as an extreme flood which appeared to trigger a bloom of *Dinophysis acuminata* in Brazil (**Luiz Mafra**) –freshening of waters, acidification and warming waters. While many of these changes are detrimental, some may reduce HAB events regionally, as conditions may become too warm for certain taxa. Climate change will make the co-occurrence of HABs and acidification more common as CO₂ levels continue to increase.

Extended bloom windows were seen in the Red Sea off the coast of Saudi Arabia, a region generally considered oligotrophic (**Afrah Al Othman**). Climate-linked changes in cyst germination phenology have been observed in *Alexandrium catenella* in the Gulf of Maine, with temperature-driven dormancy cycling producing maximum germination rates during spring (**David Ralston**). Warming trends in coastal waters may allow cysts to germinate earlier in the year, but germination rates remain in winter and early spring, resulting in little change to annual germling-flux patterns. Earlier initiation and longer inshore activity make retentive embayments key sentinels for HAB events. In the Pacific Arctic, a massive and persistent *A. catenella* cyst bed—many times

on turbulence and temperature, showing that *K. brevis* prefers warmer conditions and that storms may disrupt blooms. Climate-change-driven salinity changes have also affected HABs: freshening of northern basins appears to have led Baltic *Nodularia spumigena* strains towards long-term low salinity adaptation (**Carolin Peter**).

HABs and Social Dimensions

Several presenters focused on societal aspects of HAB research (e.g. the UN Plankton Manifesto), including what can be learnt from them (**Gustaaf Hallegraeff**). Continuing education, especially with children in rural and urban areas in Chile, highlighted community knowledge, perceptions and responses to HABs (**Pamela Carbonell**). Interviews with tourists in the intermountain region of Utah (USA) has made it possi-

ble to understand and identify the level of knowledge about HABs, offering recommendations for public institutions to develop future educational campaigns (**Hannah Bonner**). In order to understand these multifactorial processes, it is important to incorporate new tools that allow communities to more accurately understand the data that affects the local economy in the event of a HAB (**Yingze Xu**). Finally, with a vision that encompasses eleven countries in Latin America and the Caribbean, the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and the regional network REMARCO examined the current state of public policies in order to produce a regional reference document to guide and strengthen the development of national policies, thereby improving surveillance, early warning, and governance in these countries (**León Vergara**).

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All photos ICHA 2025 LOC

First record of *Gambierdiscus* cf. *australes* in Iberian Coastal Waters (western Mediterranean Sea)

Species of the genus *Gambierdiscus* R. Adachi & Y. Fukuyo (Dinophyta, Gonyaulacales) are known for their ability to produce potent polyether toxins, ciguatoxins and maitotoxins, which are responsible for ciguatera, the most prevalent and severe non-bacterial foodborne illness worldwide [1]. This syndrome arises from consumption of fish that have bioaccumulated toxins through the food web, causing gastrointestinal, neurological and sometimes cardiovascular symptoms. Ciguatera poses a major public health concern in affected areas, with an estimated incidence of 50,000 cases annually (although this figure may be underes-

timated [2]), alongside significant economic impacts on fisheries, seafood trade, and tourism [3].

Although originally considered strictly circumtropical, *Gambierdiscus* species have recently been reported in temperate waters, including the Mediterranean Sea (Greece, Cyprus, Balearic Islands) [4, 5]. Here, we report the first detection of *Gambierdiscus* cf. *australes* on the north coast of Alicante province (Spain), making this the first record of the genus on the continental coasts of the western Mediterranean basin. Molecular analyses are currently being conducted on this material to determine the specific status of *Gambierdis-*

cus cf. *australes* in Iberian coastal waters, aiming for full confirmation of its taxonomic identity.

In this study, two sampling campaigns were carried out in March and September 2023 in six zones (Racons, Marines, Reserva, Antonio, Arenal and Portitxol) along the Dénia-Jávea coast (Fig. 1), with a total of 12 sampling points (Fig. 2). Points designated as "S" were located 250 m from the coastline (depth: 5–15 m), and those labelled "P" were 1 km offshore (depth: 8–35 metres). Notably, Reserva S and Antonio S are located within the Marine Reserve of Fisheries Interest of Cabo de San Antonio. The benthic habitats in the area are heterogeneous, predominantly sandy north of the Dénia harbour and rocky to the south, with extensive seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa*) and areas of sciaphilous algae (Fig. 3). At each point, sample bottles collected at the surface and 5 m were mixed (1:1) and a 250 ml aliquot was immediately preserved with acidic Lugol's solution for further analysis. Seawater temperature was measured with a data logger JFE Advantech. While in March only Racons, Marines, Reserva and Antonio were sampled, in September all 12 points were sampled. Cellular abundance was determined according to the Utermöhl method, and species identification was performed via scanning electron microscopy (JEOL JSM-6380LV).

Gambierdiscus cf. *australes* was detected in all samples except Marines S and Antonio S collected in March. Cell concentration ranged from 20 to 140 cells·L⁻¹, with the highest abundances recorded in September (Fig. 4). Seawater temperatures in March and September ranged from 14.9 to 16.3 °C and 26.2 to 27.3 °C, respectively.

Identification of *Gambierdiscus* cf. *australes* (Fig. 5) was based on its lenticular shape, ranging from spherical to ellipsoidal in apical view and dorsoventrally compressed. Measurements included depth (D): 69–77 µm, width (W): 55–74 µm, and length (L): 33–44 µm, with D/W and L/W ratios of 1.14 and 0.6, respectively. The cell surface appeared smooth to slightly rough, with evenly distributed small pores. Plate Po was ellipsoidal, featuring a hook-shaped opening. Plate 2' was rectangular, with suture ratios of 2'1" to 2'3" = 0.69

Fig 1. View of the central area of the Marine Reserve of Fisheries Interest of Cabo de San Antonio (coast of Dénia) from the sampling point Reserva P.

Fig 2. Sampling points in the study area.

and 2'/3' to 2'/1' = 1.53. Plate 2'''' was narrow, pentagonal, and had parallel sides. The morphology and dimensions are consistent with initial descriptions from the Pacific Ocean [6] and subsequent records from other regions [7, 8].

These findings confirm the expansion of the genus *Gambierdiscus* in the Mediterranean Sea, likely facilitated by ocean currents, maritime traffic and the ongoing tropicalization of this sea. *G. cf. australes* demonstrates a high capacity for colonizing new environments beyond its historical range. Although the exact timing of this species' introduction into the coastal waters of the Iberian Peninsula remains unknown, its absence from a recent review of 30 samples collected in May and September 2011 from the same study area, performed by our research group, suggests that its arrival occurred after that year.

The colonization potential of *Gambierdiscus* poses serious challenges, as its presence may remain undetected until toxic events occur. The results obtained underline the urgent need to develop monitoring and control strategies focused on both this genus and the specific communities in which it thrives, to effectively assess the associated risks, mainly to public health and the local economy.

Acknowledgments

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Fig 3. Seagrass meadows of *Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa* and areas of sciaphilous algae at the study area.

Fig 4. Abundance of *G. australes* at different sampling points. S: shallow points. P: deep points.

Fig 5. SEM Photographs of *G. australes* from the study area. A) Epitheca. B) Hypotheca.

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The marine dinoflagellates *Heterocapsa horiguchii* and *Gambierdiscus polyne-siensis* isolated from Norfolk Island

Fig. 1. Map of Norfolk Island showing proximity to Australia and Aotearoa New Zealand.

Norfolk Island is an Australian territory lying almost equidistant from Australia and Aotearoa New Zealand (1,600 km and 1,200 km, respectively; Fig. 1). It is one of Australia's most isolated communities and oldest territories, having been settled six weeks after the founding of Sydney.

The Norfolk Island Marine Expedition in May 2025 (Fig. 2) was led by the Australian Museum [1] in collaboration with Tāmaki Paenga Hira Auckland War Memorial Museum, Te Papa Tongarewa

the Museum of New Zealand, the University of Sydney, Parks Australia, and the Norfolk Island community. The aim was to monitor, protect and understand the biodiversity of the bioregion, including collection of seawater and macroalgae samples, as previously described [2]. Samples were couriered to the Cawthron Institute to determine the microalgae present. Preserved samples were used for DNA metabarcoding, and unpreserved samples allowed isolation and culture of dinoflagellates [3].

Fig. 2. Sample collection, Norfolk Island expedition 2025. Image courtesy of Tom Bannigan.

One isolate, collected from filmy red macroalgae at a site west of 'The Arch' on the north coast, was a small fast-moving dinoflagellate which multiplied rapidly in culture (Fig. 3; maintained in f2 medium at 25°C under standard light conditions [3]). The average cell length was 25.4 µm (n=10; range 21.4–28.1 µm) and average width 16.8 µm (n=10; range 14.5 µm–18.3 µm). DNA sequencing determined the isolate to be *Heterocapsa horiguchii* Iwataki, Takayama & Matsuoka, originally described from Japanese waters [4]. It has also been reported from Chinese waters and shown to be toxic in *Artemia salina* assays and haemolytic to rabbit erythrocytes [5], making it a potential harmful algal bloom (HAB) species. The Norfolk Island isolate is now maintained in the Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae (CICCM), designated CAWD473 [6].

Heterocapsa horiguchii CAWD473 was tested for toxicity using mice by the intraperitoneal injection of culture extracts prepared according to the protocol of Munday et al. (2017) [7]. Single mice were dosed at 100, 250 and 750 mg/kg of culture extract (corresponding to 172,170,213; 430,425,531 and 1,291,276,596 cells/kg, respectively). Mice showed some initial signs of discomfort, such as abdominal stretching, but appeared normal within six hours post-dosing. In the first 24-hour period, post-dosing food intake was low, and the mice lost weight but for the following 13 days of the observational period mice gained weight with and showed normal food intake. At 14 days mice were killed, organ weights were all within normal limits. Since no toxicity was observed at any of the dose rates tested it can be concluded that the LD₅₀ of *H. horiguchii* exceeds 750 mg/kg (1,291,276,596 cells/kg) making it as of low toxicity.

While *H. horiguchii* is a new record for Norfolk Island, other *Heterocapsa* species have been reported previously from Australian waters [8]. *Heterocapsa ovata* Iwatake & Fukuyo was isolated from Coffin Bay, South Australia, in 2014 and linked to fish and oyster deaths at that time. Isolates, bioassayed for ichthyotoxicity using cells from rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) gills, were positive with the highest ichthyotoxicity observed in lysed cells. High

Fig. 3. Light micrographs of live *Heterocapsa horiguchii* cells in culture: Top, mag. x80; Bottom, mag. x200, oil immersion (actual length 13.1 μm , width 9.6 μm).

inter-strain variability suggested that different strains of *H. ovata* had varying levels of toxicity [8]. Other *Heterocapsa* species recorded in Australian waters include *H. niei* (Loeblich) Morrill & Loeblich, *H. triquetra* (Ehrenberg) Stein [9], and *H. rotundata* (Lohmann) Hansen [9-10].

Heterocapsa species previously reported in Aotearoa New Zealand include *H. niei*, *H. triquetra* [2,11] and *H. rotundata* [12] and, also *H. circularisquamata* Horiguchi and *H. illdefina* (Herman & Sweeney) Morrill & Loeblich [11].

DNA sequencing determined the *Gambierdiscus* isolate to be *G. polyneisensis*, and toxin testing [13] indicated production of both 44-methylgambierone (5 pg/cell) and gambierone (4 pg/cell). An as yet unknown compound was also detected [14] and research into this compound is ongoing. Ciguatoxins (CTXs), the cause of the serious illness ciguatera poisoning, were not detected, but as the cell concentration was low it is possible that CTXs are produced at low or even trace levels. This will be investigated further once the extremely slow growing culture begins to thrive.

Samples preserved for metabarcoding were processed as previously described, targeting the large subunit ri-

bosomal RNA gene region (D1-D2) [15]. The samples were filtered for reads identified as Dinophyceae and were dominated by reads identified as the epiphytic dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis* and the parasitic dinoflagellate genus *Amoebophrya* (Fig. 4). Other genera detected are mostly known to occupy planktonic habitats, including the genus *Heterocapsa* as reflected by the established culture. This reflects a low abundance of epiphytic/benthic taxa present in the samples. No sequence reads were identified as *Gambierdiscus* and potentially this taxon is rare and patchily distributed around Norfolk Island.

Given the proximity of Norfolk Island to northern Aotearoa New Zealand, it is only time before *H. horiguchii* and species of *Gambierdiscus* will be routinely detected in our coastal waters, and this could add a further risk to both the seafood industry and recreational fishing. They should therefore be added to those HAB species currently monitored in Aotearoa New Zealand.

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Fig. 4. Relative abundance of sequence reads identified as Dinophyceae using the large subunit ribosomal DNA region from samples collected around Norfolk Island. Genera that represent more than 1% of reads are shown.

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Dinophysis in Puyuhuapi Fjord (Chilean Patagonia): Exploring the Occurrence of Overwintering Populations in the Neuston

Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) dinoflagellate species may spend their whole life cycle as motile forms in the water column (holoplanktonic) or combine planktonic stages with a substantial part of their life as in dormancy (resting cysts) in the sediments (meroplanktonic). Dinoflagellate resting cysts are sexual life-cycle stages that play a key role in bloom initiation, termination,

and species survival when environmental conditions are not favourable for vegetative growth. The application of cysts in various fields of study, such as palaeoceanography, biogeography, ecology, phylogeny and evolution, has rapidly expanded in recent years [1,2].

The genus *Dinophysis*, includes species which are well known progenitors of one or two groups of lipophilic tox-

ins: i) okadaic acid and dinophysistoxins (aka diarrhetic shellfish poisoning or DSP toxins), and ii) Pectenotoxins. To date, despite abundant field and laboratory studies with established cultures of several species, no sexual cyst forms have been confirmed in the life history of *Dinophysis*. Past reports of putative cyst forms belonging to *Dinophysis acuta*, *D. caudata* and *D. acuminata* turned out to be pellicle (asexual) cysts of *Fragilidium*, a mixoplanktonic dinoflagellate capable of combining phototrophy with heterotrophic feeding on live prey (*Dinophysis* species). Following prey capture of specific *Dinophysis* cells, *Fragilidium* sheds its theca and forms a pellicle cyst which retains the contour of the recently ingested prey [3,4].

Currently, the most accepted hypothesis is that *Dinophysis* species survive winter conditions by adopting quiescent forms with reduced metabolism in a particular water layer until the new growth season begins [5]. Detection and quantification of *Dinophysis* populations that survive after the end of the bloom season may serve as a predictive tool for forthcoming events [6].

In this study we used neuston net hauls (Fig. 1) to explore the presence of overwintering populations of *Dinophysis* in the top 25 cm of the surface water (surface microlayer SML). This SML

Fig. 1. (A). Diagram of the frame holding the neuston net to the vessel; (B). Side view of the neuston net system attached to the vessel; (C). Using the neuston net in Puyuhuapi fjord.

Fig. 2. (A). Map of the study area showing northern Chilean Patagonia inland sea (red square indicates Puyuhuapi Fjord); (B). Puyuhuapi Fjord area and sampling stations (red circles).

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of *Dinophysis* cells (*Dinophysis acuta*, *D. acuminata* and *D. subcircularis*) recorded in the top 25 cm of the SML at the six stations.

includes the neuston layer, a particular habitat that serves as a refuge for a diverse group of organisms, including phytoplanktonic species [7]. Populations present at very low cell densities are frequently overlooked by conventional sampling methods such as oceanographic bottles, vertical net hauls, or tube samplers.

The study area was Puyuhuapi fjord (44°S, 73°W) in northern Aysén, Chilean Patagonia (Fig. 2), a well-known hotspot for *Dinophysis* (*D. acuminata*, *D. acuta*) populations. This 100-km-long fjord, characterised by a high water renewal time (~300 days in Magdalena Sound), has two connections with oceanic waters located at the mouth (Moraleda Channel) and head (Jacaf Channel). These characteristics make Puyuhuapi Fjord a suitable environment for exchange with open waters, cell accumulation and *Dinophysis* growth [8].

In June (winter) 2024, a three-day cruise was carried out along a longitudinal transect of Puyuhuapi fjord, including Magdalena Sound (Fig. 2). Samples were collected in triplicate at each station using a 3-m-long neuston net (20 µm mesh size) attached to a rectangular metal frame (1 m x 0.5 m). The net was submerged 25 cm deep and hauled from the side of the vessel for 100 m at 1–2 knots. This procedure, repeated three times per station, ensures accurate filtration of the near-surface epineuston and hyponeuston. The filtered material (25 m³ per haul) was resuspended in 1-L bottles and sieved through a 149 µm mesh to remove debris and microzooplankton. The material retained in the 149–20 µm size

fraction was resuspended in 500-ml bottles and preserved with Lugol's iodine solution (final concentration 1%). In the laboratory, total sample volumes were measured before cell counts using Sedgewick-Rafter (1 ml) chambers. The entire chamber surface was examined in three replicates, and the average result was expressed as cells m⁻³.

Three species of *Dinophysis* were identified: *Dinophysis acuminata*, *D. acuta* and *D. subcircularis*. Maximal cell densities were found at the mouth of the fjord (Station 1); densities were very low or below detection limits at the inner station close to the fjord head. *D. acuminata* (2.4 x 10³ cells m⁻³) was the most abundant species, *D. acuta* was rare (max. 40 cells m⁻³) and *D. subcircularis* showed a maximum at Station 1 and remained below 30 cells m⁻³ at the other five stations (Fig. 3). This common distribution pattern for the three species suggests that inoculum populations originate outside the fjord.

In summary, horizontal SML net hauls with a neuston net revealed the presence of winter populations of several *Dinophysis* species. This method substantially improves the detection of low-density populations inhabiting poorly explored parts of the water column. Preliminary results shed light on the potential source of inoculum populations that eventually develop dense blooms in Puyuhuapi fjord. An inoculum that originates in outer parts of the fjord and is subsequently advected and grows in the inner zones may represent a potential mechanism and life-cycle adaptation enabling success in fjord systems

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Not all troubles come from toxins: a list of non-toxic animal killer microalgae

Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) encompass a wide range of events caused by diverse microalgae that can affect human and animal health, ecosystems, and seafood security and have economic consequences. Given the variety of targets and causative organisms, it is unsurprising that the mechanisms of impact differ among HAB types. Based on affected resources and mechanisms, HABs can be roughly subdivided into four categories (Table 1).

Regarding human health, microalgal toxins may act directly through contact or aerosol exposure, but more commonly they accumulate in seafood and can cause harm even at low cellular concentrations (Table 1A). The responsible organisms are generally well known, and include several diatoms, dinoflagellates and cyanobacteria. Different mechanisms of action and human syndromes have been identified. Fortunately, fatal cases are limited because monitoring of phytoplankton and shellfish toxicity in harvesting areas is generally mandatory. However, toxin concentrations in seafood exceeding regulatory limits often result in temporary harvesting

bans, with consequent economic losses for the shellfish industry. Additionally, unregulated seafood consumption represents a risk in areas where toxic species proliferate.

Of a different nature are toxic events causing mass mortalities or injuries to marine organisms, including pen fish, cultivated bivalves and wild fauna (Table 1B). Several microalgae producing bioactive extracellular compounds affecting animal health—such as ichthyotoxins, reactive oxygen species (ROS), and haemolysins—have been documented [see 1 for review]. These organisms mostly belong to dinoflagellates but also to other phototrophic flagellates (e.g., raphidophytes and dictyochophytes). Their toxins are distinct from those affecting human health, though in some cases microalgae toxic to humans can also harm marine animals or impair their reproductive ability [2–4].

Both types of toxic microalgae mentioned above (ca. 270 species) are listed in the IOC- UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Algae [5], a catalogue providing taxonomic, toxicological, morphological, and molecular information for each potentially toxic species. The list was initiated in the 1990s, on the recommendation of the IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB) to provide a unified database supporting research and monitoring. An editorial panel of taxonomy experts supervises and periodically updates the list [6]. A recent improvement added 44 cyanobacteria to the list, which initially focused only on marine species.

However, microalgae can also cause damage without producing toxins. Injuries or mortality of wild and cultivated marine fauna have frequently been associated with blooms of organisms not known to produce toxins (Table 1C), while seawater discolouration, mucilage, foams and/or unpleasant odours have caused problems in areas used for tourism and recreation (Table 1D). A comprehensive list of these non-toxic yet harmful microalgae has long been requested by the scientific and management communities but has been challenging to compile. Non-toxic taxa are part of the normal microflora, with harmful effects only occurring under specific conditions. While toxic species can be rapidly identified through chemical and morphological analyses, pinpointing the causative non-toxic species can be difficult, particularly in multispecies blooms. Additionally, the boundaries of such a list are uncertain because any microalga reaching high abundance can potentially harm marine life [7].

Acknowledging these caveats and recognizing the importance of identifying potentially harmful non-toxic species, we prepared a preliminary list based on documented cases from the Harmful Algae Event Database (HAEDAT, <https://haedat.iode.org/>) and peer-reviewed literature. The compilation was organized in two steps. The first step addressed non-toxic species associated with occasional or recurrent impacts on marine fauna (Table 1C). By design, toxic species were excluded even if other mechanisms of impact were involved.

Among 913 HAEDAT-reported animal mortality or impairment events (as of October 2025), 142 were linked to 37 taxa not known to produce toxins. Additional cases from reviews [e.g.,

Table 1. Schematic subdivision of HABs based on their impacts. Not all types of impacts are covered, and boundaries among these categories are not sharply defined. Some human toxins (A) can also affect animals (B), while many toxic species (A and B) can damage animals via mechanisms other than their known toxins (C), e.g., oxygen depletion, or produce discolourations or mucilage, impacting tourism (D). Toxic species are recorded in the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae [5], whereas the new list presented here concerns C-type species [9]. A list of species involved in D-type HABs is in preparation.

<p>A. Toxic to humans</p> <p>Toxins accumulate in seafood or irritate the skin or respiratory system</p> <p>Impacts on human health and aquaculture</p> <p>Examples: <i>Alexandrium</i> spp., <i>Dinophysis</i> spp., <i>Prorocentrum</i> spp., <i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> spp., cyanobacteria spp.</p>	<p>B. Toxic to marine fauna</p> <p>Ichthyotoxins and other bioactive compounds damage tissues</p> <p>Impacts on the health of wild and cultured marine animals</p> <p>Examples: <i>Karenia</i> spp., <i>Heterocapsa</i> spp., <i>Margalefidinium</i> spp., <i>Chattonella</i> spp., <i>Chrysochromulina</i> spp.</p>
<p>C. Harm to marine fauna with no toxins</p> <p>Physical damage to gills via spines or mucus, oxygen depletion, or starvation</p> <p>Impacts on the health of wild and cultured marine animals</p> <p>Examples: <i>Noctiluca scintillans</i>, <i>Chaetoceros</i> spp., <i>Octactis</i> spp., <i>Triplos</i> spp., <i>Aureococcus anophagefferens</i></p>	<p>D. Harm to human activities</p> <p>Discolourations, mucilage, foams, and unpleasant odours</p> <p>Impacts on tourism, recreational, and commercial activities</p> <p>Examples: <i>Gonyaulax fragilis</i>, <i>Thalassiosira mala</i></p>

8] or peer-reviewed papers involved 30 more taxa [9]. To date, 25 diatoms, 31 dinoflagellates, four dictyochophyceans, two pelagophyceans, one cryptophycean, one raphidophycean, two chlorophytes, and the mixotrophic ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum* (Fig. 1) are included in the new list on the website of the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Algae, in the section 'Harmful non-toxic' species (<https://www.marinespecies.org/hab/nontoxic.php>). Species names in the list are updated according to the current nomenclature and linked to their respective WoRMS pages [10]. A downloadable Excel file summarises 120 documented cases supporting taxa inclusion, including 56 verified HAEDAT events and additional literature reports. For each case, the file provides location, time, impact, literature or HAEDAT reference, and a quality flag evaluating identification methods. Multiple events for some species are listed to indicate spatial and temporal incidence without aiming for exhaustiveness. The list is updated periodically, and contributions from the scientific community to improve its completeness and accuracy are encouraged.

An analysis of 210 HAEDAT and literature records (Fig. 2) shows that the dinoflagellate *Noctiluca scintillans* is the taxon most frequently associated with non-toxic harmful events (16% of cases), involving mortality of fish — including salmon, demersal and cultured species — as well as benthic invertebrates. Reports of such impacts span globally distant regions including the Indian and Indonesian coasts (Indian Ocean), Gulf of Trieste (Mediterranean Sea), South China Sea (Pacific Ocean), and Irish and South African coasts (North East and South East Atlantic). Other frequently represented dinoflagellates include species belonging to *Prorocentrum*, *Triplos*, and *Gonyaulax* (9, 8 and 8%, respectively). Among diatoms, *Chaetoceros* with gill-damaging setae (9%) and *Skeletonema* spp. (7%) were most frequently associated with harmful events. The dictyochophyceans *Octactis* spp. and *Dictyocha* accounted for 6% of cases. The ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum*, included because of its microalgal symbiont, was involved in 7% of the cases, while the pelagophytes *Aureococcus* and *Aureoumbra* contributed 3%. Harmfulness is supported by mul-

Fig. 1. Taxonomic composition of the list of species not known to produce toxins but responsible for injuries or death in marine animals.

multiple independent events for these taxa, whereas it remains uncertain for 41 species that were associated with only a single reported event.

A second list, also based on HAEDAT and the literature, is presently in preparation and will include species producing seawater discoloration, mucilage, foams, unpleasant odours (Table 1D), and other impacts on water quality and human activities.

Mechanisms behind non-toxic animal-kills are often poorly understood. In some *Chaetoceros* species and dictyochophyceans, the spiny siliceous cell structures damage the gills of both fish

and invertebrates, leading to suffocation [11] (Fig. 3A). Gill clogging and suffocation can also result from mucus produced by some diatoms or dinoflagellates (e.g., *Thalassiosira mala* and *Gonyaulax fragilis*). In many other cases, the decay of massive blooms (e.g., *Triplos* spp., *Prorocentrum* spp., and *Noctiluca scintillans*) depletes oxygen and can generate hydrogen sulphide, causing asphyxia and poisoning in animals unable to escape (Fig. 3B). Malnutrition due to the small size of the available prey has caused growth arrest and mortality in oysters in Thau Lagoon, France [12], during massive blooms of

Fig. 2. Relative contribution of non-toxic species to harmful events affecting marine animal health, based on 210 cases reported in HAEDAT or in the literature. The ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum* is included because of its photosynthetic microalgal symbionts. The majority (61%) of the non-toxic animal-killer species are associated with only one harmful event.

Fig. 3. Examples of injuries to marine fauna caused by microalgae, with no involvement of toxic substances. (A). Gill degeneration induced by the long siliceous setae of some diatoms in the genus *Chaetoceros* [11]. (B). A massive mortality of fish in St Helena Bay, on the South African west coast, in March 1994 due to hypoxia and hydrogen sulphide development following a bloom of *Tripos furca* and *Prorocentrum micans* — Argo photograph (C). Plumage fouling in seabirds due to the high concentration of proteinaceous substances produced by a bloom of *Akashiwo sanguinea* [14].

the trebouxiophycean *Picochlorum tauri*. Peculiar cases concern the diatoms *Coscinodiscus centralis* and *C. concinnus*, which produce oily substances that fouled birds' feathers, causing death by drowning [13], and the dinoflagellate *Akashiwo sanguinea*, which releases proteinaceous substances that also caused plumage fouling [14] (Fig. 3C). However, the latter species is not included in the new list, because it is already in the main catalogue with other ichthyotoxic species.

The list of non-toxic species should be interpreted cautiously, particularly for species associated with only one or a few events. Multispecies blooms complicate the identification of causative species, and undetected toxic species may be present. In addition, the boundary between the lists of toxic and non-toxic fish killers is at times vague. Some of the species listed among the latter, e.g., the pelagophytes *Aureococcus anophagefferens* and *Aureoumbra lagunensis* and the dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum micans*, were moved from the main catalogue to the new list due to a lack of evidence of their capacity to produce toxins *de novo*. Conversely, future studies may discover the capacity to produce toxins in some taxa now considered non-toxic. Additional information, corrections and suggestions are welcome

to enhance the list, with the hope that this initial effort will stimulate the description of similar events in HAEDAT or in the literature, thus expanding the knowledge on these natural phenomena that can damage marine life.

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From GEOHAB to GlobalHAB and Beyond: How 30 years of International Coordination of Research on Harmful Algal Blooms Will Inform the Next Ten Years

The International Conference on Harmful Algae convened in Punta Arenas, Chile from 19–24 October 2025, provided an excellent opportunity to reflect on past, present and future internationally coordinated research on Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs). This was achieved through a plenary talk by Elisa Berdalet (Vice-Chair of the last GEOHAB Scientific Steering Committee – SSC – and former Chair of the GlobalHAB SSC) and a town hall led by Clarissa Anderson (current Chair of the GlobalHAB SSC) (Fig. 1)

HABs are a global problem that require both *local* solutions and *international* coordination. In 1998, this vision motivated a partnership between the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) to develop a programme for coordinating

international research on HABs: GEOHAB, the *Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms*. In 2000 and 2001, respectively, the Scientific and Implementation Plans of GEOHAB were published (Fig. 2), with the *overarching goal of improving prediction of HABs by determining the ecological and oceanographic mechanisms underlying their population dynamics, integrating biological, chemical, and physical studies supported by enhanced observation and modelling techniques*.

The GEOHAB programme was structured around five Elements that served as a framework to guide priorities and research: 1) Biodiversity and Biogeography; 2) Nutrients and Eutrophication; 3) Adaptive Strategies; 4) Comparative Ecosystems; and 5) Observation, Modelling, and Prediction (Fig. 3). Between 2000 and 2015, activities and prod-

ucts delivered under GEOHAB included Open Science Meetings, Workshops, Scientific Networking, Capacity Building, Reports, Special Issues and Books co-funded by SCOR and IOC, alongside contributions from local, national and regional entities. These efforts were implemented with strong engagement

Fig. 1. Elisa Berdalet (former Chair of the GlobalHAB SSC) showing publication products of the international programme during her plenary talk, at the 21st ICHA, Punta Arenas, chaired by Clarissa Anderson (current Chair).

Fig. 2. Science Plans of the GEOHAB (top, <https://oceanexpert.org/doclist/73>) and GlobalHAB (bottom, <https://oceanexpert.org/document/21016>) programmes.

Fig. 3. Themes integrated into the GlobalHAB Science and Implementation Plan (<https://oceanexpert.org/document/21016>), ranging from small-scale subjects to ecosystem-scale studies and climate-change-related processes.

from the international HAB scientific community through projects endorsements.

During the 2012 Open Science Meeting held at the IOC Headquarters in Paris, France, the international community reviewed the GEOHAB programme and recognized the continuing need for international research coordination to accelerate understanding of HAB organisms and associated events, as well as to advance predictive capacity for management and mitigation. The robustness of the GEOHAB Scientific Programme was acknowledged, forming the basis for a new research phase on HABs, with innovative objectives driven by the new programme *GlobalHAB*. After a transition period devoted to final synthesis products from GEOHAB and development of the new GlobalHAB Science and Implementation Plan, GlobalHAB was launched in 2016 for an additional ten year period.

GlobalHAB was designated as a SCOR–IOC programme whose primary mission is to address the contemporary scientific and societal challenges related to HABs by adopting a multidisciplinary approach involving the evaluation and application of advanced technologies, training and capacity building, and information and dissemination activities. The programme has become synonymous with cutting-edge science co-designed to support local, regional, national, and global decision-making on all aspects of HABs. As with GEOHAB, wide international participation of both the research community and stakehold-

ers has been essential to the success of GlobalHAB. Recently, complementary global initiatives, such as The UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030) ('the Ocean Decade'), have provided an ideal landscape for the GlobalHAB Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) to shape the next era of GlobalHAB activities for another ten years.

At ICHA2025, participants were invited to join the GlobalHAB SSC at a special town hall to provide feedback on the new activities proposed in *The Next Ten Years of GlobalHAB (2026–2035: Science and Implementation Plan*, in lieu of another Open Science Meeting. This plan was previously presented to the

IOC-convened Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB), a group of representatives from IOC Member States tasked with coordinating global responses to the HAB problem. It was also shared with the broader oceanographic community at a town hall hosted by the GlobalHAB SSC during the One Ocean Science Congress in Nice, France from 2–6 June 2025.

In Chile, David Clarke from the Marine Institute (Ireland) represented the ICES–IOC Working Group on HAB Dynamics (WGHABD), while Philipp Hess from Ifremer provided insights into how the new UN Decade Programme, HAB Solutions (HAB-S), is expected to integrate recommendations from GlobalHAB and other complementary programs into solutions addressing present-day HAB challenges (Fig. 4). Clarissa Anderson then presented the major goals proposed in the Science and Implementation Plan, which span many cross-cutting UN Sustainable Development Goals: **1**) Emerging Threats: Characterizing invasion ecology and changing biogeography of potential HAB species (SSC leads: Raffaele Siano, Silvia Nascimento, Hae-Jin Jeong); **2**) Food Security and Human Health: (a) Codify methodologies to understand the threats and impacts posed by HABs to fisheries and aquaculture (SSC Leads: Jorge Mardones, Aletta Yniguez, Hae-Jin Jeong), (b) Freshwater HAB Impacts on human, animal, and ecosystem health (SSC Leads: Malin Olofsson, Heather

Fig. 4. The HAB-Solutions Programme: a Proposed Action for the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development by the IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on HABs (<https://oceandecade.org/actions/harmful-algae-bloom-solutions/>). For more information, contact Henrik Enevoldsen (IOC-UNESCO, h.enevoldsen@unesco.org), Philipp Hess (Ifremer, Philipp.Hess@ifremer.fr) and Maggie Broadwater (NOAA, maggie.broadwater@noaa.gov).

Raymond); **3) Food Web Complexity Influencing HAB Dynamics:** (a) Use new methodologies in genomics to define the role of tropho-dynamics in structuring HAB occurrence, frequency, intensity, and food web impacts (SSC Leads: Luisa Mangialajo, Dave Clarke, Aifeng Li); (b) Apply improved detection techniques and experimental approaches to move towards a predictive understanding of regulations on toxin production phases, mechanisms of harm, and reverberating effects in food webs (SSC Leads: Aifeng Li, Jorge Mardones, Raffaele Siano); **4) Benthic HABs:** Ecological studies including species ecophysiology, biotic interactions, responses to nutrient enrichment, to a changing climate, and to habitat destruction, besides bloom impacts on ecosystem and human health (SSC Leads: Luisa Mangialajo, Elisa Berdalet, Silvia Nascimento); **5) Automated HAB Detection and Predic-**

tion: Apply advanced remote sensing, machine-learning modeling techniques, and in situ observing to HAB detection, prediction, and operational forecasting for mitigation and spatial/temporal awareness of bloom transport (SSC: Clarissa Anderson, Aletta Yniguez, Dave Clarke); **6) Marine HAB control and its interaction with the environment – bio-feedbacks from mitigation interventions** (SSC Leads: Jorge Mardones, Dave Clarke).

At least 60 international HAB experts contributed ideas for shaping the next phase of GlobalHAB. Community members expressed strong support for the draft plan, interest in engagement and providing support, and offered new workshop and project ideas aligned with specific goals. The most discussed topics were Emerging Threats, Food Security and Human Health, Food Web Complexity, and Marine HAB Control.

Anyone interested in providing input on the plan or becoming more involved with GlobalHAB is encouraged to consult the [draft plan](#) and contact the GlobalHAB Chair at clrande@ucsd.edu.

Thanks for your interest: together, we built GEOHAB and GlobalHAB, and together we will build the next ten years of GlobalHAB Science!

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Guidelines for the study of climate change effects on HABs

GLOBAL Harmful Algal Bloom: status report 2021

2025 IOC Training Course and Identification Qualification in Harmful Marine Microalgae 2025

On 18-27 November 2025, the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae at the University of Copenhagen, Denmark organised the 2025 IOC Training Course and Identification Qualification in Harmful Marine Microalgae. The purpose is to improve the taxonomic and identification skills of the participants for research purposes and for practical monitoring of harmful algal blooms.

The IOC has organised training courses on harmful microalgae since 1993. Since 2006, the IOC training in HAB identification has been offered within a framework that gives accreditation. The training includes a practi-

cal exam at the end of the course that issues participants with an *IOC Certificate of Proficiency in Identification of Harmful Algae*. Many of the hundreds of trainees over the years have specifically been seeking accreditation, and in some countries, the IOC course has become a reference for laboratories to be approved for carrying out regulatory monitoring of harmful microalgae.

The training course includes 100 hours of teaching and is divided into two parts. The first part of the course is held online using IOC's e-learning platform *OceanTeacher Global Academy* and gives general introductions to the various groups of harmful algae; this part is

mainly for self-study and estimated at 40 hours of reading. The second part is a practical course in species identification including 60 hours of teaching and microscopy.

This year, participants came from Australia, Germany, India, Ireland, the Netherlands, Norway, Romania, Saudi Arabia, UAE and the UK.

The course is addressed to participants that have some years of practical experience in identification of microalgae and priority is given to applicants who have direct research or management responsibilities regarding the occurrence of harmful algae. This year's lecturers were Dr. Jacob Larsen, Dr. Santiago Fraga, Professor Nina Lundholm and Professor Øjvind Moestrup.

For more information, please contact Jacob Larsen, jacobl@bio.ku.dk.

The 2025 Course participants behind an amazing collection of Dinoflagellate wood carvings provided by Dr. Takayama (Japan) to be used as species models at the IOC training course.

ISSHA Societal Activities during the 21st ICHA Conference

The International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) co-convoked the 21st International Conference on Harmful Algae, held in Punta Arenas, Chile, from 19–24 October 2025. The ISSHA Council held various meetings between January and October 2025 to organize a range of conference activities, Council elections, travel awards, achievement awards, and the ISSHA General Assembly.

Conference activities included an ISSHA stand coordinated by Mary Carmen Ruíz de La Torre, with the help of many students, whose support was greatly appreciated (Fig. 1). ISSHA and ICHA stickers, designed by Lorena Durán Riveroll, were available at the ISSHA stand. Photographs were kindly provided by Mitsunori Iwataki, Koyo Kuwata, Carol Waldmann Rosenbaum, and Alenza Lancaster, our thanks to all. ISSHA also organized an auction, coordinated by Luiz Mafra with the excellent support of many students who carried out all the work behind-the-scenes and elegantly presented the items on stage. Thanks to the many generous donations of auction items from conference participants, the efforts of auctioneers Catharina Alves-de-Souza and Dedmer Van de Waal, and the enthusiastic bidding, a total of 4,071 USD was raised, which will be fully used for student travel awards for ICHA 2027.

General Assembly

The ISSHA General Assembly was held on Monday 20 October from 19:00 to 20:30. The meeting was opened by President Dedmer Van de Waal, after which various updates were presented, including proposed by-law changes (Ian Jenkinson; see below), achievement awards (see below), the secretary's report (kindly prepared by Ingrid Sassenhagen), the treasurer's report (Yasmine Bottein), updates on publications and dissemination including the ICHA 2023 Proceedings and ICHA 2025 special issues, Travel Awards (Po Teen Lim; see below), Council election results (see below), an update on the Young Investigator Network Meeting (Misty Peacock; see below), details regarding ICHA2025 (Leonardo Guzmán), and a presentation

of the ICHA 2029, which will be held in Halifax, Canada (Pearse McCarron).

By-law changes

The proposed and approved by-law changes included the addition of a new early-career Webmaster position in the ISSHA Council. The position was created because the workload of the student representative, combined with the growing demands of managing the website, had become too heavy for one person. The vote was unanimous in favour of creating the new position. A discussion followed regarding the visibility of ISSHA through social media, potentially with the assistance of early-career scientists from the membership. The ISSHA Council will consider this further and revisit the topic at ICHA 2027.

Young Investigators Network Meeting

This networking event was organized on Sunday 19 October by Misty Peacock and Megan Schulz. It consisted of several activities, including speed-science conversations, unconference hot-topics, and an 'Ask an Expert' with guests Vera Trainer, Raphael Kudela, and Dedmer Van de Waal. The event was very well attended, with a total of 56 early-

career scientists including early-career researchers, PhD students, and undergraduate students.

Travel Awards

Travel awards were granted to 28 young researchers and ISSHA members to support their participation at ICHA 2025. The call for applications was announced on the ISSHA website six months before the event, and applicants submitted their applications via a Google form. The call was also circulated by email to reach a wider audience in the HAB research community. All applications were evaluated by the ISSHA Travel Award Committee.

With funding from the Scientific Committee on Ocean Research (SCOR), four young scientists from developing countries (Argentina, Brazil (two), and China) were selected. ISSHA provided 13 additional travel awards funding by the society, supporting members from Australia, Iceland, Mexico (four), Ireland (two), Portugal, the Philippines, the United Kingdom, and Spain. In addition, eleven applications from nine United States institutions were supported with funding from NOAA (USA), to support their attendance to ICHA 2025.

In 2025, ISSHA also launched two additional travel-support schemes: one for retired scientists and one for scientists from underrepresented countries. Travel support for retired scientists was

Fig. 1. Students in action at the fund-raising stand during ICHA 2025, Punta Arenas, Chile (photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

made possible through a very generous contribution from an ISSHA member, for which we are very grateful. This has supported three retired scientists to attend ICHA 2025. Support for underrepresented countries was funded through sponsorship by the publishers of *Harmful Algae* (Elsevier), *Marine Drugs* and *Toxins* (MDPI), and supplemented with ISSHA funds. This has supported four scientists from South Africa, Mexico, Guatemala, and Kazakhstan to attend ICHA 2025.

ISSHA Council members

ISSHA members voted online for the Executive Council, Council members, early-career Webmaster, and student representative. Several Council members stepped down after years of active service, including Ian Jenkinson, Esther Garcés, Tim Harwood, Leila Basti, and Luiz Mafra. On behalf of ISSHA, Presi-

dent Dedmer Van de Waal thanked all outgoing members for their contributions. Special thanks were given during ICHA 2025 to Ian Jenkinson for his long-standing service to the ISSHA Council.

The new ISSHA Executive and Council for the 2025–2027 term (new members and executive positions are in **bold**):

Executive Council

President: Dedmer Van de Waal (The Netherlands)
 Vice-President: Lorena Durán Riveroll (Mexico)
 Vice-President: **Uwe John** (Germany)
 Treasurer: Yasmine Bottein (France)
 Secretary: Ingrid Sassenhagen (Germany)
 Past-President: Wayne Litaker (USA)

Council members

Antonella Penna (Italy)
 Christine Edwards (United Kingdom)
 Henrik Enevoldsen (Denmark)
 Laura Biessy (New Zealand)
Malin Olofsson (Sweden)
 Mary Carmen Ruiz de la Torre (Mexico)
Máximo Frangopulos (Chile)
 Mitsunori Iwataki (Japan)
Oyeshina Oyeku (Nigeria)
 Philipp Hess (France)
 Po Teen Lim (Malaysia)
Sam Murray (New Zealand)
 Shauna Murray (Australia)
 Toshiyuki Suzuki (Japan)

Webmaster: **Fredrik Ryderheim** (Sweden)
 Student Representative: Carolin Peter (Denmark)

The profiles of the ISSHA Council members can be found on the ISSHA website at ISSHA Council (<https://issha.org/members-community/issha-council/>).

ISSHA 2025 Achievement Awards

Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award

The ISSHA 2025 Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award was presented to **Vera Trainer** (University of Washington, USA) for her influential work on harmful algae, leadership in the field with major contributions to both science and society, and her long-standing services to the national and international HAB research community. The nomination of Vera Trainer was led and presented by Lisa Campbell during the award ceremony at ICHA 2025. (Figs. 2, 3)

Vera Trainer has dedicated her life's work to high-quality research and leadership in major marine science organizations related to Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs). She served as President of ISSHA and as Chair of the Science Board of the North Pacific Marine Science Organization (PICES). In addition to her leadership roles, Dr. Trainer has mentored new and established researchers, helping them advance the field, engage with affected communities, and elevate the standards of HAB research through intellectual professionalism. Students,

faculty, and colleagues recognize her profound contributions and can trace her influence in their own HAB research pathways. Her achievements in HAB research and outreach form the foundation of her success at every level.

Dr. Trainer is among the leaders of HAB research along the Pacific Ocean's eastern shores. She has established effective and impactful HAB monitoring collaborations in these waters involving federal, state and local agencies,

Fig. 2. Sam Murray (Patrick Gentien Awardee) and Vera Trainer (Yasumoto Awardee) with their Takayama carved favourite HAB species (photo Vera Trainer).

Fig. 3. Vera Trainer is presented the Yasumoto Awards by ISSHA President (right) and Liza Campbell (left) (photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

coastal tribes, academic partners, and community volunteers. She led the creation and implementation of the IOC Global Harmful Algal Information System (HAIS) and was instrumental in establishing HAB training programs in developing countries, including the Philippines, Indonesia and Guatemala. She is a global authority on the toxigenic diatom, *Pseudo-nitzschia*.

For 30 years, Vera has conducted innovative HAB research, including evidence-based assessments, the development of the Domoic Acid Dipstick Test Kit, and inexpensive field assays. She has also designed early warning models for PSP, ASP, and DSP events. As a leading scientist, she has directed HAB research to focus on purposeful, community-based initiatives and has emphasized the significance of connections between Tribal and scientific communities, providing training and insights to diverse, self-managing communities. Dr. Trainer designed the Marine Biotoxin Program and the Sound Toxins partnership, a volunteer-based early warning system for HABs monitoring efforts with federal, state and local agencies, coastal tribes, and academics. She has demonstrated exceptional leadership across various fields, including toxin biochemistry, environmental impacts, fish kills, and marine mammal ailments.

Her work aims to connect oceanographic conditions with toxic HABs and identify conditions of enhanced harm. Her research has significant implications, affecting essential fisheries, higher trophic levels, and environmental resource management.

Patrick Gentien Young Scientist Award

The ISSHA 2025 Patrick Gentien Young Scientist Award was awarded to Sam Murray (Cawthron Institute, New Zealand) for his outstanding contributions to HAB research, including his work on ciguatera poisoning, national risk assessment efforts, and training programmes for local and Indigenous communities. His nomination was led by Lesley Rhodes and presented by Kirsty Smith during the award ceremony at ICHA 2025 (Fig. 4). Sam Murray was awarded his PhD in 2022 for his thesis on the identification and structural elucidation of toxins associated with ciguatera poisoning. Since then, in his postdoctoral research, he has continued to focus on this critical area, making significant contributions to the scientific understanding of toxins produced by benthic dinoflagellates. Sam is an active member of the Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) research community, regularly attending ICHA conferences and recently initiating collaborative projects with scientists in Germany, Spain, Canada, and several Pacific Island nations. He is particularly recognized for 1) his impactful research on ciguatera poisoning, supporting the resilience and self-sufficiency of Pacific Island communities; 2) his involvement in New Zealand's national efforts to assess the risks of ciguatera-producing organisms in the rapidly warming northern coastal waters of

Aotearoa New Zealand; and 3) his work training local and Māori communities in northeastern Aotearoa New Zealand in the use of rapid screening tools for assessing the safety of recreationally harvested shellfish.

Dr. Murray exemplifies scientific excellence, regional leadership, and a deep commitment to community-centered research. His work spans the ecological, toxicological, and public health dimensions of HABs, with a particular focus on the dinoflagellates *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa*, the primary organisms responsible for ciguatera poisoning. His interdisciplinary approach has significantly advanced understanding of the distribution and behavior of these toxic algae in tropical and subtropical reef ecosystems across the Pacific. He maintains a strong commitment to Pacific Island communities, where ciguatera poisoning remains an under-recognized yet persistent public health challenge. He has led numerous collaborative projects with local institutions in Fiji, Tonga, the Cook Islands, and Kiribati. These initiatives aim to build local capacity for ciguatera monitoring, develop culturally appropriate risk communication tools, and inform regional fisheries policy. His work directly supports food security and public health resilience in some of the Pacific's most vulnerable coastal populations. This is also exemplified by his contributions to strengthening laboratory

Fig. 4. Sam Murray is presented the Patrick Gentien Award by ISSHA President with Kirsty Smith (photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

Fig. 5. Maureen Keller Oral presentation Awardees (left to right): Jaume Reverte, Dedmer Van de Waal (ISSHA President), Karin Garefelt and Francesca Cucchi (photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

Fig. 6. Dedmer Van de Waal (left) and Maureen Keller poster awardees, Ambbar Aballay-González and Flávio Oliveira, with Philipp Hess (right) (photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

capabilities in Papua New Guinea, the Solomon Islands, Fiji, and Kiribati. His support includes delivering hands-on training and helping to implement quality assurance systems and chemical testing methods tailored to the needs of each country. His emphasis on sustainability and local ownership ensures that scientific capacity remains embedded within the communities he supports.

ISSHA 2025 Maureen Keller Awards

We congratulate all students who presented a talk or poster at ICHA 2025. The overall quality of the presentations was exceptionally high, with exciting advances across the broad field of HAB research. We particularly highlight those who received the highest scores and were awarded the ISSHA 2025 Maureen Keller Awards. We thank the many judges involved for their valuable support (Figs. 5-7). The ISSHA 2025 Maureen Keller oral presentation awards were won by **Francesca Cucchi** (“*Intra- and inter-specific transcriptomic profiling of *Alexandrium* strains from Irish waters and the North Sea to identify novel molecular markers associated with toxins production*”), **Jaume Reverte** (“*An Electrochemical Immunosensor for Tetrodotoxin and Saxitoxin*”),

Detection: A Step Towards Integrated Seafood Toxin Monitoring”), and **Karin Garefelt (“*From pixels to patterns: Automated in situ imaging reveals diel vertical migration among phytoplankton*”). The responses from the judges unanimously positive, highlighting the clarity**

Fig. 7. Maureen Keller Poster awardee Victoria Vossler and ISSHA President (photo ICHA 2025 LOC).

of the slides and the quality of the presentations.

The ISSHA 2025 Maureen Keller poster presentation awards were won by **Ambbar Aballay-González** (“*In vitro assessment of saxiphilin C-lobe as a saxitoxin-neutralizing agent*”), **Victoria Vossler** (“*Mitigation of *Karenia brevis* Using Natural Products*”), and **Flávio Oliveira** (“*Taxonomic and biochemical characterization of a novel Altericista cyanobacterial strain from the Mondego River, Portugal*”). The judges were impressed by the clarity of the posters, and specifically applauded the novelty of the presented topics.

Short biosketches of the ISSHA 2025 Maureen Keller award winners can be found on the [ISSHA website](https://www.issha.org/).

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Courses 2026

IOC Identification Qualification in Harmful Marine Microalgae 2026 (Registration to open shortly)

OCHABs-IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae International Phytoplankton Inter-comparison (IPI) test 2026 (Registration to open shortly)

<https://hab.ioc-unesco.org/>

<https://www.icmss.net/>

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